

Potential and Limitation of PlanetScope Images for 2-D and 3-D Earth Surface Monitoring with Example of Applications to Glaciers and Earthquakes.

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1. NAIP and LiDAR data

The horizontal geolocation accuracy of PS L3Bs images is assessed by cross-correlating PS images with a mosaic of 65 aerial images acquired in 2020. The aerial images are publicly available through the National Agriculture Imagery Program (NAIP) and distributed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer website.

In addition, a reference DEM generated from LiDAR acquisition in 2016 over Ridgecrest is used to evaluate the pre-and post- PlanetScope DSMs.

2. Supplementary figures

Fig.S 1 Ground displacement maps using Dove-R orthoimage product (L3Bs). Each panel represents the North/South components of the horizontal displacement. Maps in the first row represent (corresponds to) the horizontal displacement between two pre-earthquake images acquired on 2019-06-06 and 2019-06-21, respectively. Maps in the second row correspond to the displacement between a pre-earthquake image acquired on 2019-06-06 and a post-earthquake image acquired on 2019-09-17. columns represent the resulting displacement using the 4 spectral bands of Dove-R (Blue, Green, Red, and Near-Infrared, respectively).

Fig.S 2 East-West displacement components computed using L3B Dove-C images over Ridgecrest region. (a) E/W map between two pre-earthquake descending mosaic images acquired on June 04 and 30, 2019,

respectively. (b) E/W map between two ascending mosaic images bracketing the seismic event, acquired on June 30 and July 09, 2019, respectively. (c) E/W map resulting from the correlation of two mosaic images of a mixture of ascending and descending orbit direction scenes acquired on June 30 and July 09, 2019, respectively.

Fig.S 3 Interbrand displacement maps computed using a mosaic of ascending L3Bs Dove-C images bracketing the seismic event acquired on June30 and July 09, 2019, respectively.

Fig.S 4 Dove-R cross band correlation over Ridgecrest

Fig.S 5 Interbrand correlation disparity maps of a SuperDove image acquired on June 29,2020 over the Ridgecrest region.

Fig.S 6 Dove-R North/South coseismic surface displacement maps of Ridgecrest earthquake before and after using geoPCAIM reconstruction.

Fig.S 7 Dove-C North/South coseismic surface displacement maps of Ridgecrest earthquake before and after using geoPCAIM reconstruction.

Fig.S 8 EW components

Fig.S 9 Post earthquake L1B Dove-C images over Ridgecrest ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 10 Pre-earthquake L1B Dove-C images over Ridgecrest ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 11 2016 L1B Dove-C images over Shisper ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 12 2017 L1B Dove-C images over Shisper ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 13 2019 L1B Dove-C images over Shisper ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 14 2020 L1B Dove-C images over Shisper ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 15 2020 L1B Dove-R images over Shisper ROI. (a) Image count. (b) Image footprints. (c) Histogram of image pairs overlap.

Fig.S 16 Flowchart illustrating a nominal work flow to generate displacement maps using PlanetScope ortho images.

Table S. 1 Ridgecrest Dove-C L1Bs data description

Image ID	Instrument	Sat Id	Prod Type	Acquisition Date	AcquisitionTime	GSD	Orbit Direction	Incidence Angle	Azimuth Angle	View Angle
Ridgecrest Pre-earthquake										
20190629_181110_1003_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1003	L1B	6/29/2019	18:11:10+00:00	3.85	DESCENDING	2.18	11.95	1.99
20190629_181111_1003_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1003	L1B	6/29/2019	18:11:11+00:00	3.85	DESCENDING	2.18	11.95	1.99
20190629_181112_1003_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1003	L1B	6/29/2019	18:11:12+00:00	3.85	DESCENDING	2.18	11.94	1.99
20190629_181109_1003_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1003	L1B	6/29/2019	18:11:09+00:00	3.85	DESCENDING	2.18	11.96	1.99
20190630_171006_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:06+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.31	-11.70	3.03
20190630_181106_1038_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1038	L1B	6/30/2019	18:11:06+00:00	3.88	DESCENDING	5.45	11.79	4.98
20190630_171007_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:07+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.30	-11.69	3.02

20190630_181104_1038_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1038	L1B	6/30/2019	18:11:04+00:00	3.88	DESCENDING	5.43	11.81	4.96
20190630_181308_1027_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1027	L1B	6/30/2019	18:13:08+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	2.17	12.24	1.97
20190630_181107_1038_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1038	L1B	6/30/2019	18:11:07+00:00	3.88	DESCENDING	5.47	11.79	5.00
20190630_171005_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:05+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.30	-11.69	3.02
20190630_181103_1038_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1038	L1B	6/30/2019	18:11:03+00:00	3.88	DESCENDING	5.44	11.81	4.97
20190630_181231_1011_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1011	L1B	6/30/2019	18:12:31+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	3.22	12.22	2.94
20190630_171004_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:04+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.31	-11.69	3.03
20190630_181310_1027_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1027	L1B	6/30/2019	18:13:10+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	2.17	12.22	1.97
20190630_181230_1011_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1011	L1B	6/30/2019	18:12:30+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	3.25	12.23	2.96
20190630_181105_1038_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1038	L1B	6/30/2019	18:11:05+00:00	3.88	DESCENDING	5.45	11.79	4.98
20190630_181229_1011_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1011	L1B	6/30/2019	18:12:29+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	3.21	12.22	2.93
20190630_181309_1027_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1027	L1B	6/30/2019	18:13:09+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	2.16	12.23	1.96
20190630_171008_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:08+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.30	-11.70	3.03
20190630_181307_1027_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1027	L1B	6/30/2019	18:13:07+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	2.17	12.22	1.97
20190630_181228_1011_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1011	L1B	6/30/2019	18:12:28+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	3.22	12.23	2.94
20190630_181311_1027_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1027	L1B	6/30/2019	18:13:11+00:00	3.84	DESCENDING	2.17	12.22	1.97
20190630_171008_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:08+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.29	-11.71	3.02
20190630_171009_100d_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	100d	L1B	6/30/2019	17:10:09+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.30	-11.72	3.03
20190604_171715_0f36_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f36	L1B	6/4/2019	17:17:15+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.25	-11.33	2.99
20190604_171713_0f36_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f36	L1B	6/4/2019	17:17:13+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.25	-11.32	2.99
20190604_181115_1009_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1009	L1B	6/4/2019	18:11:15+00:00	3.85	DESCENDING	1.12	12.16	0.99
20190604_171712_0f36_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f36	L1B	6/4/2019	17:17:12+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.24	-11.32	2.98
20190604_171714_0f36_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f36	L1B	6/4/2019	17:17:14+00:00	3.61	ASCENDING	3.24	-11.33	2.98
Ridgecrest Post-earthquake										
20190717_181038_1004_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1004	L1B	7/17/2019	18:10:38+00:00	3.91	DESCENDING	5.46	11.81	4.98
20190717_181036_1004_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1004	L1B	7/17/2019	18:10:36+00:00	3.91	DESCENDING	5.46	11.83	4.99
20190717_181039_1004_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1004	L1B	7/17/2019	18:10:39+00:00	3.91	DESCENDING	5.44	11.81	4.96
20190717_181037_1004_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	1004	L1B	7/17/2019	18:10:37+00:00	3.91	DESCENDING	5.44	11.82	4.96
20190709_170913_10f46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:13+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.33	-11.73	3.98
20190709_170915_0f46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:15+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.32	-11.73	3.97
20190709_170910_0f46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:10+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.33	-11.70	3.98
20190709_170911_0f46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0f46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:11+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.35	-11.71	3.99

20190709_170914_Of46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	Of46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:14+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.34	-11.72	3.99
20190709_170912_Of46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	Of46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:12+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.35	-11.71	3.99
20190709_170913_Of46_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	Of46	L1B	7/9/2019	17:09:13+00:00	3.59	ASCENDING	4.33	-11.72	3.97
20190707_181335_101f_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	101f	L1B	7/7/2019	18:13:35+00:00	3.87	DESCENDING	4.38	12.35	4.00
20190707_171112_104a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	104a	L1B	7/7/2019	17:11:12+00:00	3.58	ASCENDING	0.13	-11.53	0.09
20190707_181338_101f_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	101f	L1B	7/7/2019	18:13:38+00:00	3.87	DESCENDING	4.41	12.32	4.02
20190707_171115_104a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	104a	L1B	7/7/2019	17:11:15+00:00	3.58	ASCENDING	0.14	-11.55	0.10
20190707_181339_101f_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	101f	L1B	7/7/2019	18:13:39+00:00	3.87	DESCENDING	4.40	12.31	4.01
20190707_171113_104a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	104a	L1B	7/7/2019	17:11:13+00:00	3.58	ASCENDING	0.14	-11.54	0.10
20190707_171114_104a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	104a	L1B	7/7/2019	17:11:14+00:00	3.58	ASCENDING	0.14	-11.54	0.10
20190707_181336_101f_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	101f	L1B	7/7/2019	18:13:36+00:00	3.87	DESCENDING	4.39	12.34	4.00
20190713_180748_0e3a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0e3a	L1B	7/13/2019	18:07:48+00:00	3.95	DESCENDING	5.39	12.27	4.92
20190713_180744_0e3a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0e3a	L1B	7/13/2019	18:07:44+00:00	3.95	DESCENDING	5.38	12.34	4.90
20190713_180747_0e3a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0e3a	L1B	7/13/2019	18:07:47+00:00	3.95	DESCENDING	5.40	12.34	4.93
20190713_180745_0e3a_1B_AnalyticMS.tif	PS2	0e3a	L1B	7/13/2019	18:07:45+00:00	3.95	DESCENDING	5.40	12.35	4.93